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SURVEY

A Systematic Review on Gait Analytics in Disorders With Motor Phenotypes Utilizing Inertial Measurement Units and Plantar Pressure Sensors

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ABSTRACT Among the 97 studies included in this systematic review, 81 (83.5%) investigate Parkinson's Disease (PD), reflecting the broader research landscape and the established utility of wearable sensors in capturing PD-specific gait impairments rather than an intentional PD-focused search strategy. Building on this context, this review synthesizes recent advances in gait analytics using Inertial Measurement Units (IMU) and Plantar Pressure Sensors (PPS) across disorders with motor phenotypes. Gait analysis has emerged as a critical tool for understanding motor dysfunction, enabled by portable sensor technologies capable of precise, real-time measurements in naturalistic settings. This review, spanning publications from 2020 to April 2024, examines studies identified through four major databases (PubMed, Scopus, IEEE Xplore, and Google Scholar). Eligible works were original, peer-reviewed studies applying quantitative gait analytics using IMUs and/or PPS in Arthritis, Diabetes Mellitus, or PD. Exclusion criteria comprised non-human studies, incompatible sensing modalities, use of more than ten different sensors, sensor-comparison-only studies, absence of gait protocols, and cohorts consisting solely of healthy individuals or those with gait-altering deformities. Together, IMUs and PPS are reshaping diagnostic and monitoring strategies for PD, Arthritis, and Diabetes, where gait abnormalities and neuropathic complications are central to functional impairment. Beyond PD, the review includes 12 Diabetes and 4 Arthritis studies, representing peripheral nerve and musculoskeletal conditions that remain comparatively underexplored. The included studies are synthesized by sensor modality, placement, analytical methodology, protocol design, cohort characteristics, and performance outcomes. Approaches ranged from statistical analysis to machine learning, deep learning, and rule-based models, with several reporting state-of-the-art results. The findings underscore the value of wearable sensors for monitoring disease progression, detecting gait-phase abnormalities, and supporting personalized interventions. Despite these advancements, significant limitations persist, including a lack of publicly available datasets, limited external validity, small or imbalanced samples, inconsistent sensor placement, and data integration challenges. Future directions emphasize standardized protocols, multi-center validation, and AI-driven multimodal fusion to unlock scalable, clinically reliable gait-analytics solutions across healthcare and rehabilitation.

INDEX TERMS Analytics, artificial intelligence, arthritis, diabetes mellitus, gait analysis, inertial measurement units, Parkinson's disease, plantar pressure sensors, wearables.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Gait, the manner or pattern of walking, is a fundamental component of human movement and an indirect indicator

FIGURE 1. The right gait cycle decomposed into events and phases. Events occur at typical timings: initial contact (0%), opposite toe-off (~10%), heel rise (~30%), opposite initial contact (~50%), toe-off (~60%), feet adjacent (~73%), tibia vertical (~87%), and the next initial contact (100%). Stance (~60%) comprises loading response, mid stance, and terminal stance with two brief periods of double-limb support (loading response and pre-swing); swing (~40%) comprises initial, mid, and terminal swing. Colored bars indicate the clinical tasks: weight acceptance, single-limb support, and limb advancement. [1].

of health and functionality. It involves a complex biomechanical process requiring coordination among muscles, bones, and the nervous system. Gait analysis examines parameters, events, and phases of the walking cycle—such as stride length, cadence, velocity, and the stance and swing phases—offering detailed insights into walking mechanics. Gait spatiotemporal parameters (GSTPs) quantify aspects like timing, rhythm, and spatial features, making them essential for identifying normal and pathological gait patterns and for clinicians, researchers, and therapists in assessing interventions, tracking rehabilitation, and diagnosing gait abnormalities.

Key GSTPs include gait speed (GS), which measures walking efficiency; cadence (C), indicating step rhythm; and stride length (SdL), affecting both GS and C. The gait cycle spans from one heel strike (HS) to the next of the same foot, comprising the stance phase (StP)—when the foot is grounded—and the swing phase (SwP)—when the foot moves forward. StP begins with HS, followed by flat foot (FF), heel off (HO), and toe off (TO). SwP begins after TO and includes foot clearance. StP also includes periods of single support (SS) and double support (DS), relevant to gait stability. Step length (SpL) is the distance from one HS to the next of the opposite foot, with other key parameters including step width (the lateral distance between the feet during walking), toe-out angle (the angle between the direction of walking and the line of progression of each foot), and foot clearance.

Fig. 1 illustrates the various stages and phases of the right gait cycle, which is the sequence of movements that occurs during a single step from one HS to the next HS of the same foot. It breaks down the cycle into specific events such as initial contact (IC), opposite TO, heel rise (HR), opposite IC, TO, feet adjacent, tibia vertical, and the next IC, marking key moments during the walking process.

The cycle is divided into distinct periods: loading response (LR), mid stance (MSt), terminal stance (TSt), pre swing (PSw), initial swing (IS), mid swing (MSw), and terminal swing (TSw). Each period corresponds to a specific task, such as weight acceptance, single-limb support, or limb advancement. These tasks are further categorized into the StP, where the foot is in contact with the ground, and the SwP, where the foot moves forward in the air. The image provides a detailed, sequential overview of the gait cycle, highlighting the timing and coordination of different parts of the body as they contribute to walking.

Gait analysis provides direct information about locomotion and is widely used in diagnosing and monitoring disorders such as Parkinson's disease, cerebral palsy, and others. It also has applications in security (e.g., biometric identification and surveillance) and sports (performance enhancement and injury prevention). Traditionally, gait analysis has relied on motion capture and force plate systems in controlled environments, offering high-accuracy data on ground reaction forces (GRF) and kinematics but with limited accessibility and naturalism. In contrast, Inertial Measurement Unit Sensors (IMU) and Plantar Pressure Sensors (PPS) enable real-time, continuous, precise, and portable gait monitoring. IMUs (accelerometers, gyroscopes, magnetometers) capture body kinematics, while PPS insoles measure force distribution and gait symmetry, key for cost-effective, in-situ analysis.

In the last few decades, gait analysis has become integral to diagnosing and treating motor disorders and disorders with motor phenotypes. Disorders affecting gait can be broadly categorized into neurodegenerative, peripheral nerve, and musculoskeletal conditions, each impacting motor function through distinct physiological mechanisms. Neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's Disease (PD), Multiple Sclerosis (MS), and Friedreich's Ataxia (FA) lead to abnormalities due to progressive central nervous system impairment, resulting in features like bradykinesia, ataxia, and spasticity. Peripheral nerve disorders, including Diabetes Mellitus with peripheral neuropathy (DPN), Myasthenia Gravis, and Muscular Dystrophy, interfere with motor signal transmission, producing characteristic gait alterations such as foot drop or fatigability. Musculoskeletal disorders, exemplified by Arthritis, disrupt joint mechanics and stability, leading to compensatory gait adaptations. Gait analytics offer valuable insights into these disorders by quantifying abnormal patterns and supporting tailored interventions. This review focuses on one representative condition from each category, Parkinson's Disease (neurodegenerative), Diabetes Mellitus (metabolic disorder with peripheral neuropathy), and Arthritis (musculoskeletal), due to their significant and system-spanning effects on gait. To this end, the review focuses on these three broad categories: neurodegenerative disorders, disorders with peripheral nerve involvement, and musculoskeletal disorders, reflecting the coordination among muscles, bones, and the nervous system.

Recent advancements use gait state machines, machine learning (ML), and algorithmic tools to annotate gait data

into phases and extract C, stride, and acceleration-based features. These feed Artificial Intelligence (AI) models that detect disease presence or progression based on motor impairment. This pipeline is shaped by sensor type, positioning, data acquisition protocols, methodology, algorithm selection, and performance metrics. This review explores how gait analytics—specifically using IMUs and PPS—are transforming the diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment of motor disorders. By characterizing unique gait patterns per disorder group, it supports more precise interventions. The study contributes by:

- Presenting an overview of the current state of the art in quantitative gait analysis using IMUs and PPS.
- Providing key insights into existing gait analytics, including the modalities used, their positioning, gait features, methodology, algorithms, and performance.
- Showcasing the current applications of IMUs and PPS in healthcare.
- Discussing the issues, challenges, and future directions for researchers and clinicians.

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section II outlines the methodology for identifying relevant literature; Sections III-V present categorized findings; Section VI provides research trends and proposes future directions; Section VII discusses the findings, challenges and research opportunities; Section VIII concludes the review.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodological approach adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines [2], which consist of four key steps: identification, where relevant studies are systematically retrieved from selected databases; screening, where duplicates and clearly irrelevant records are excluded based on titles and abstracts; eligibility, where full-text articles are evaluated against predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria; and inclusion, where the final set of studies is selected for detailed review. This structured process ensures transparency, consistency, and reproducibility throughout the review. A comprehensive literature search was conducted across four cloud-based databases—PubMed, Scopus, IEEE Xplore, and Google Scholar—covering the period from 2020 to 2024. This timeframe was selected to capture the most recent advancements in gait analytics relevant to healthcare, and the final search was performed on April 30, 2024. Figure 2 presents the PRISMA flow diagram detailing the systematic review process. The search strategy combined terms related to gait analysis and specific review disorders, Diabetes Mellitus, Arthritis, and Parkinson's Disease, along with keywords such as “acceleration,” “IMU,” “pressure,” and “wearables.” The search yielded 325 records, with 48 duplicates removed, leaving 277 unique manuscripts for screening.

Following duplicate removal, 277 records underwent title and abstract screening. A total of 151 studies were excluded based on predefined criteria, including being non-original

FIGURE 2. PRISMA flowchart illustrating the systematic process of article inclusion and exclusion, detailing the criteria applied at each stage of the review to ensure a precise and transparent selection of studies.

works (e.g., reviews, conference abstracts), analytics-free, involving non-human subjects, irrelevant sensing modalities (e.g., MRI, CT, video), or lacking gait-related protocols. Additional exclusions were made for studies involving sensor validation, exercise interventions, unrelated deformities, or exclusively healthy participants.

The remaining 126 studies progressed to full-text review, where 29 were further excluded for reasons such as exceeding the sensor count threshold (more than 10), using incompatible modalities (e.g., force platforms, cameras), or being non-peer-reviewed literature (e.g., dissertations). The threshold of ten sensors was selected due to larger multi-sensor configurations substantially increasing energy consumption and power-management demands [3], complicating synchronization and data communication, introducing safety and mobility concerns for PD patients, where numerous body-worn devices can become obstructive and unsuitable for daily living, and significantly reduce practicality and user acceptance [4]; moreover, only one such study was excluded, which used whole-body sensor placement (i.e., head, hands, upper and lower back, legs, etc.) and did not contradict the conclusions of this review but instead reinforced the PD-related findings. Ultimately, 97 studies met the eligibility criteria and were included in the review. These 97 records were categorized according to the disorders with motor phenotypes investigated: 81 focused on Parkinson's Disease, 12 on Diabetes Mellitus, and 4 on Arthritis. Inclusion criteria were narrowly defined to ensure that only studies applying gait analytics with wearable or portable sensors, specifically

IMUs and PPS, in the context of these disorders were considered. The high representation of PD-related studies appears to mirror broader trends in the research landscape, potentially driven by the high utility of IMUs and PPS in the prognostic, diagnostic, and therapeutic management of PD, particularly for monitoring medication effects, tailoring treatment regimens, and assessing motor response to dopaminergic therapies in real-world environments.

A. SYSTEMATIC QUALITY & RISK-OF-BIAS APPRAISAL

The body of literature analyzed spans heterogeneous sensing modalities, algorithmic pipelines, experimental protocols, and performance reporting standards, making formal risk-of-bias appraisal tools difficult to apply consistently (e.g., Newcastle–Ottawa Scale). Nevertheless, the review incorporates a structured quality-appraisal process that addresses the core bias domains assessed in these frameworks.

To ensure methodological rigor and reduce selection bias, two independent reviewers (D.G.B. & G.M.) screened all records and performed full-text evaluations. Each study was initially classified as relevant, uncertain, or irrelevant based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Consensus for uncertain cases was reached through discussion with a third reviewer acting as mediator (E.M. or D.I.F.). This multi-reviewer process mitigated subjective bias and ensured transparency and reproducibility in the selection procedure. Importantly, the overall screening and decision-making workflow was directly informed by systematic selection strategies [5], whose framework emphasizes explicit decision rules, structured reviewer collaboration, and traceable documentation to improve repeatability and robustness in systematic literature studies.

A detailed data-extraction framework was developed to systematically capture methodological and analytical characteristics of each study. The framework included fields directly relevant to quality appraisal, such as: (i) disease focus and clinical objective; (ii) sensing modality and hardware specification; (iii) sensor placement and protocol design; (iv) preprocessing and feature-extraction methods; (v) ML or statistical techniques used; (vi) validation strategies, including cross-validation, external testing, or comparative baselines; (vii) sample size and demographic distribution; (viii) performance metrics and uncertainty reporting; (ix) study limitations; and (x) software and analytical tools. These categories reflect bias dimensions commonly evaluated in Quality Assessment of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies 2 (e.g., index-test bias, flow and timing), Newcastle–Ottawa Scale (e.g., comparability, selection), and Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (e.g., methodological coherence, reporting quality). However, these formal tools were not applied here, as they are primarily designed for clinical systematic reviews rather than heterogeneous, engineering-oriented studies such as those included in this work.

During data extraction, any methodological inconsistencies or missing details were documented. When

additional bias-relevant information was encountered, such as non-standard validation procedures, small or unbalanced cohorts, lack of external testing, or unclear preprocessing, the extraction form was updated accordingly, and previously extracted studies were revisited to ensure uniformity. This iterative process allowed for identification of potential sources of bias related to study design, sensor configuration, analytic choices, and performance interpretation.

It should be highlighted that no study that met the relevance and eligibility criteria was excluded on the basis of quality alone. Instead, quality-related characteristics were captured, reported, and considered during synthesis rather than used as exclusion criteria. This decision aligns with PRISMA principles, which emphasize complete and transparent reporting of included studies and discourage selective exclusion based on subjective judgments of quality. In this context, presenting the full set of eligible studies ensures that the heterogeneity and current methodological boundaries of wearable-sensor gait research are accurately reflected rather than masked through selective filtering. This inclusive approach is further supported by study-selection research showing that structured, consensus-driven decision strategies reduce the risk of unintentionally excluding relevant evidence and improve the repeatability of systematic reviews.

In addition, an internal, non-quantitative quality structuring scheme was used to support narrative synthesis across the highly heterogeneous literature. This internal framework was designed to highlight the most widely acknowledged methodological challenges in wearable gait-analysis research, namely limited cohort sizes, cohort imbalance, restricted validation strategies, and incomplete performance reporting. Specifically, study characteristics related to (i) cohort size and distribution, (ii) use of explicit validation procedures (e.g., cross-validation, leave-one-subject-out, train-test-split, or external testing), and (iii) reporting of performance metrics beyond overall accuracy (e.g., sensitivity, specificity, AUC, or error measures) were systematically considered during synthesis. This internal structuring device was used exclusively to guide comparative interpretation and narrative emphasis and was not employed to exclude studies, compute pooled estimates, or assign formal quality weights. Its purpose was to ensure that recurring methodological limitations were consistently and transparently reflected in the presentation of results, rather than being addressed implicitly or ad hoc across sections.

Collectively, the appraisal framework provides a systematic and transparent assessment of the methodological quality of the included studies, while acknowledging that heterogeneity across sensing technologies, machine-learning workflows, and experimental environments limits the applicability of traditional clinical bias-assessment tools. The approach used here captures equivalent quality dimensions in a manner appropriate for engineering-focused gait-analysis research, enabling meaningful synthesis and comparison across the diverse literature base while maintaining transparency and adherence to PRISMA standards.

III. DIABETES MELLITUS

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) presents significant global health challenges, with complications affecting multiple parts of the body. Among these, diabetic foot ulcers (DFU) are particularly concerning due to their high prevalence and association with lower limb amputation. Monitoring gait in diabetic patients using advanced analytics based on IMUs and PPS offers a promising strategy for early detection and management of such complications. Gait abnormalities in diabetic patients, often resulting from DPN, serve as early indicators of foot-related complications. These abnormalities, manifested as changes in GS, SdL, and plantar pressure distribution, are influenced by chronic sensory and motor impairments associated with hyperglycemia and are key markers for DFU development.

Wearable IMUs and PPS provide granular data on gait characteristics. Strategically placed on the lower body or footwear, IMUs measure GSTPs such as step time (SpT), C, GS, and SdL, while PPS capture dynamic plantar pressure and foot contact area. These sensors enable the detection of subtle gait deviations that can be overlooked in conventional assessments. Given the strong correlation between gait abnormalities and DFU risk, continuous gait monitoring is essential for timely intervention and prevention of ulcer progression and amputation. Integration with advanced algorithms and AI models further enhances diagnostic accuracy and prediction capabilities.

Recent literature has emphasized various analytic approaches to gait data in diabetes. Descriptive analytics summarize historical data through metrics such as mean and standard deviation, paired with visualization tools to reveal trends. Diagnostic analytics identify causal factors and patterns through correlation and root cause analyses, shedding light on the underlying mechanisms of diabetic gait impairment.

Predictive analytics apply models such as regression, support vector machines (SVM), and neural networks (NN) to forecast future gait patterns and complications, supporting proactive care. Prescriptive analytics extend this by recommending interventions to mitigate anticipated risks, using decision analysis to inform clinical action. Inferential analytics generalize findings from sample data to broader populations through hypothesis testing, confidence intervals, and inferential regression, allowing researchers to draw population-level conclusions about gait alterations in diabetes.

Table 1 summarizes selected studies on gait analytics in individuals with diabetes and arthritis. Descriptive studies characterize the distributions of gait and plantar pressure without focusing on diagnostic outcomes [6], [7], [8], [9]. Pressure insoles have gained clinical popularity for their practicality in both controlled and real-world environments. For example, variations in strain location and StP under different walking speeds and inclinations were analyzed using Kruskal-Wallis, Wilcoxon, and Shapiro-Wilk tests.

Results showed that increased walking speed elevated strain by 15–25% and reduced stance time, while inclined walking shifted strain from the hindfoot to forefoot, increasing it by 20–30% [6].

DPN and Peripheral Arterial Disease (PAD), common diabetes-related complications, significantly impair motor function. DPN causes nerve damage and loss of sensation, while PAD reduces blood flow, heightening the risk of foot ulcers and amputation. A study using insoles and Kolmogorov–Smirnov and ANOVA tests found that both DPN and PAD significantly increased forefoot peak pressure, with the DPN-PAD group showing reduced midfoot contact and anterior displacement of the center of pressure [7]. Similarly, dynamic plantar pressure profiles revealed that patients with diabetic neuropathy had higher dynamic peak plantar pressure (DPPP, $P = 0.035$) and medial heel segmental peak pressure (SPPP, $P = 0.009$), although changes in contact area were not statistically significant [8].

As diabetes progresses, sensory impairments, including reduced proprioception and vibration perception, lead to unsteady gait, poor coordination, and increased fall risk. One study found deep sensory impairment correlated with lower GS, reduced C, smaller SdL, and increased StP [9]. All gait parameters correlated significantly with superficial sensory loss ($P < 0.01$), and vibratory sensitivity was lower in T2DM than T1DM ($P < 0.05$), with longer diabetes duration linked to reduced vibration sensitivity.

Diagnostic studies aim to differentiate diabetic from non-diabetic gait or detect complications using wearable sensors and analytics [10], [11], [12], [13]. IMUs placed on the lower back were used for Fourier and power spectral analysis. The acceleration signal was first filtered using a 4th order Butterworth band-pass filter with a range of 0.2–15 Hz. A 256-point fast Fourier transform with Welch's method with a periodic Hanning window and 50% overlap revealed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in GS and Step Speed (SpS) between diabetic and control groups, alongside a lower dominant frequency in diabetics [10]. Convolutional neural network followed by long short term memory architecture (CNN-LSTM) models trained on raw IMU data classified diabetic vs. healthy gait with up to 91.25% accuracy, 93.43% F1 score, and 96.7% AUC [12]. A simpler multilayer perceptron (MLP) achieved 85.84% accuracy and 90.16% F1 using only 1,701 parameters vs. 70,881 in the CNN-LSTM model [13], both trained on the same dataset [14]. Plantar pressure mats, using logistic regression and ROC analysis, showed that peak plantar pressure (PPP) above 40.2 N/cm² strongly correlates with high-risk feet and DFUs, especially at the 1st and 5th metatarsal heads and midfoot [11].

Predictive studies forecast diabetic complications using wearable sensors [15], [16], [17], [18]. Specialized footwear equipped with accelerometers and pressure films revealed that landing and swing angles were significantly lower in diabetic patients with and without DPN ($P < 0.05$) [15]. Vibration perception thresholds (VPT) also predicted gait

outcomes; SpT AUC for DPN detection was 0.608 with a cutoff of 538.41 ms [16]. Early gait changes in T2DM without clinical DPN were also studied. Compared to controls, T2DM patients had shorter stride length (0.94 m vs. 1.04 m, $P = 0.000$), slower walking speed (2.64 km/h vs. 2.96 km/h, $P = 0.001$), and reduced oscillation speed (1.23 vs. 1.33, $P = 0.002$) [17]. A Random Forest (RF) model predicted T2DM using gait features with 0.857 accuracy and 0.94 AUC. Gait has also been linked to cognitive function in mid-life T2DM patients. IMU data showed significantly slower GS in normal and fast walking ($P < 0.001$), longer SdT, and greater gait complexity compared to healthy controls [18]. Gait velocity correlated with global cognition and domains including visuospatial function and memory. A novel “complexity index” based on multiscale entropy captured gait signal complexity. NN and linear regression models showed comparable performance in predicting cognitive outcomes.

In summary, gait analytics using IMUs and PPS, integrated with ML, offer a framework for diagnosing, monitoring, and predicting diabetic complications. These systems enable early identification of gait changes, support timely interventions, and enhance patient outcomes. The correlation between gait and cognition in T2DM further underscores the broader clinical relevance of gait analysis in diabetes care.

IV. ARTHRITIS

Arthritis comprises a wide range of inflammatory joint disorders that affect millions globally, often resulting in pain, stiffness, swelling, and impaired mobility. These symptoms contribute to motor dysfunction and distinct gait abnormalities. Common forms such as Psoriatic Arthritis (PsA), Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis (JIA), and knee pain-related conditions, including flexible flatfoot, significantly impact gait and physical function. Gait analytics—leveraging technologies like IMUs, PPS, and AI—offers objective insight into these impairments, supporting improved diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment planning.

A study on PsA employed body-worn IMUs to evaluate GSTPs, including C, GS, SdL, SwT, and DS [19]. Patients with PsA demonstrated significant gait variability and instability compared to controls ($P < 0.006$). C and GS were lower, while DS time was elevated, correlating strongly with foot pain and disability scores. These findings confirm IMUs as effective tools for assessing functional impairment in PsA. Furthering this approach, researchers used foot-worn PPS and AI to detect knee pain during gait [20]. Pressure distribution data were converted into heatmap images, filtered using a modified hybrid method (RMSE = 2.748; PSNR = 39.35). The k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm achieved 99.44% accuracy, demonstrating the promise of combining plantar pressure data with supervised learning for arthritis diagnostics.

In pain management, a study introduced a real-time gait feedback device comprising a knee orthosis and vibration motor regulated by foot pressure data from a piezoelectric

plate [21]. The system translated pressure into electrical signals to modulate vibration intensity during the StP. A strong correlation ($r = 0.85$) was observed between foot pressure and vibration output, and the device reduced pain intensity by 80% in initial tests, illustrating the potential of real-time feedback systems in geriatric arthritis care.

Another study applied piezoresistive sensors and KNN classifiers to detect knee pain with 99.44% accuracy [22]. Focusing on critical gait events like HS and TO, the system identified pressure patterns strongly associated with reported knee pain ($p < 0.05$), reinforcing the utility of sensor-based gait monitoring in routine clinical assessment.

Collectively, these studies demonstrate the efficacy of advanced gait analytics in identifying and managing gait dysfunction in arthritis. IMUs, PPS, and AI tools enable precise detection of gait abnormalities, enhancing diagnostic accuracy and personalizing interventions. As these technologies evolve, they offer significant potential for integrating gait analysis into arthritis research and clinical practice, ultimately improving outcomes and quality of life for patients.

V. PARKINSON'S DISEASE

PD is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder marked by the degeneration of dopamine-producing neurons, leading to motor impairments such as tremors, bradykinesia, rigidity, and postural instability. Gait disturbances, including shuffling, reduced arm swing, and slowed movement, are among the most disabling symptoms, increasing risk of falling and hindering daily function. Consequently, gait analysis has become essential for diagnosing PD, tracking disease progression, and evaluating therapeutic outcomes.

This systematic review categorizes recent studies on gait analysis in PD into six key areas:

- a) Freezing of Gait (9 manuscripts): Focused on detecting and predicting episodes in which patients temporarily lose the ability to initiate or continue walking despite the intention to do so.
- b) Gait Events and Phases Estimation (12 manuscripts): Aimed at accurately identifying distinct gait phases and events in patients with PD.
- c) Correlations of Gait Spatiotemporal Features with PD and Healthy Controls (18 manuscripts): Comparative studies examining differences in gait features between PD patients and healthy individuals.
- d) Falls Prediction (3 manuscripts): Investigations into predicting fall risk in PD patients through gait metrics.
- e) Turning Points/Turns (3 manuscripts): Analyses of turning movements, which pose heightened difficulty and often worsen gait instability in PD.
- f) Gait Patterns, Diagnosis, and Severity (36 manuscripts): Research exploring characteristic gait features in PD and their associations with diagnosis and disease severity.

TABLE 1. Selected manuscripts with analytics for diabetes mellitus and arthritis linking sensor modality to gait features and analytic methods, including findings, protocol and cohort details.

Ref.	Modality	Gait Features	Algorithms (Type)	Key Findings	Protocol	Cohort Details
[8]	Pressure mat	<i>DPPP, SPPP, C</i>	One-way ANOVA, Tukey HSD test (Descriptive)	$P = 0.035$ for DPPP difference between diabetic neuropathy and control groups	Walk on a 2-meter pressure mat barefoot; static pressure recorded during relaxed stance	53 subjects: 15 subjects with T2DM, 24 with T2DM but without any foot deformity, and 14 healthy control subjects (47.17 ± 9.69 years)
[9]	IMU sensor at lumbar area (L5 spinal segment)	<i>S, C, Lstride, CD, StP, SwP, SS, DS, Lstep, Stance, Var, Vmax, GAcc, Gdece</i>	Logistic Regression (Descriptive)	$P < .05$ for deep sensory pathways correlation with gait parameters	Walk as usual for 15 meters. Pause for 3 seconds both before and after the halfway point, and then proceed back to the start	85 diabetic patients aged 68.1 ± 1.3 years, 46-39 males-females
[11]	Pressure mat	PPP at 12 distinct plantar sites (i.e., toes, metatarsal heads, midfoot, and heel)	Logistic Curve, ROC/AUC Analysis (Diagnostic)	Diabetes sites with $PPP > 58.83 \text{ N/cm}^2$ six times more likely to have DFU history ($p < 0.0001$)	Participants walked barefoot on a carbon footprint mat, capturing PPP at each site during one full gait cycle	33 participants: 21 diabetes patients with previous DFU (60.7 ± 9.5) (95.2% male), 12 healthy controls (58.5 ± 8.3) (33.3% male)
[19]	6x IMU Sensors at chest, lower back, wrists, and feet	<i>C, GS, SdL, SwP, CD, DD, Anglestrike, Varsdt</i>	Paired t-, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, ANCOVA, Pearson's and Spearman's correlation coefficients (Descriptive & Predictive)	Lower cadence, gait speed, stride length, and swing time; higher gait cycle duration, Stride time variability and double support time in PsA group ($p < 0.006$).	Three trials of a 10-meter walk test at comfortable speed	21 PsA patients 76%female, aged 53.9 ± 8.9 years), 21 healthy controls (76%female, aged 54.2 ± 9.3 years)
[22]	Foot-worn piezoresistive sensor insole embedded with 102 sensors	Foot pressure distribution, HS, FF, HO, SwP	KNN, DT, SVM, LR, NB (Predictive)	KNN achieved accuracy of 99.44%. RMSE for the modified hybrid filter was 2.748, and PSNR was 39.35 for image enhancement. GLCM-based feature extraction.	Each subject walked a distance of 10 meters five times	36 subjects aged 17-65 years, including 22 arthritis patients and 14 healthy volunteers.

IMU: Inertial Measurement Unit, DPPP: Dynamic Peak Plantar Pressure, SPPP: Segmental Peak Plantar Pressure, C: Cadence, S: Speed, Lstride-SdL: Stride Length, StP: Stance Phase, SwP: Swing Phase, Var: Variability, Vmax: Maximum Velocity, Gacc: Gradient Acceleration Gdece: Gradient Deceleration, SS: Single Support, DS: Double Support, Lstep-SpL: Step Length, GS: Gait Speed, HS: Heel Strike, FF: Flat Foot, HO: Heel Off, TO: Toe off

A. FREEZING OF GAIT

Freezing of gait (FoG) is a disabling motor symptom of Parkinson's Disease, characterized by brief, episodic inability to step forward despite the intent to walk. Commonly occurring during gait transitions like turning or gait initiation, FoG significantly reduces quality of life due to its unpredictability and its association with motor and cognitive impairments. Wearable sensors and AI have recently emerged as powerful tools for FoG detection and prediction, enabling timely intervention and continuous monitoring. This section reviews recent studies that employed sensor-based approaches and ML algorithms for FoG analysis, focusing on their performance, methodology, and limitations.

In [23], researchers combined handcrafted features (e.g., Freezing Index, entropy measures) with deep features learned through a ResNeXt CNN, using gait acceleration data from

the DAPHNet dataset (10 PD patients, 8 with FoG). The hybrid model achieved a 95.4% prediction accuracy, demonstrating that integrating manual and deep features enhances performance. However, limited generalizability due to small sample size remains a concern. In a similar vein, [24] used the DAPHNet dataset with data augmentation and SMOTE techniques to enhance model robustness. They evaluated Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), Extra Trees (ET), and a Transformer model. LDA achieved the highest FoG prediction accuracy (99.21%), while XGB (96.40%) and ET (96.21%) also performed well. Optimal pre-FoG labeling (7 s window) and ankle sensor placement were crucial to model accuracy.

In [25], bilateral stepping coherence was used to predict FoG using wearable sensors on 14 PD patients. A novel Synchronization Loss Threshold (SLT) detected FoG on

average 1.81 s before onset (vs. 0.22 s for voluntary stops). The SLT-based model achieved 98% sensitivity and 42% specificity, though turning-related misclassifications reduced accuracy. A topological approach using nonlinear dynamics and phase space reconstruction was explored in [26]. Acceleration data from 8 PD patients were used to extract features like Betti curves and persistence landscapes. Their generic model achieved 91.93% sensitivity, 87.61% specificity, 89.76% accuracy, and AUC of 0.956; even higher accuracy was reported for person-specific models.

Utilizing the same dataset, the authors in [27] introduced a “transition” class before FoG onset and tested five ML models (RF, XGB, GB, SVM-RBF, MLP). The SVM-RBF achieved best results, with sensitivity of 72.34% (FoG), 91.49% (transition), and 75.00% (normal), and specificity of 87.36%, 88.51%, and 93.62%, respectively. In [28], 71 participants with FoG completed a FOG-provoking test across three conditions (i.e., single, dual-motor, and motor-cognitive tasks), using three Opal sensors at lower back and ankles. An SVM-RBF classifier achieved 85% accuracy, 84.1% sensitivity, and 83.4% specificity, with performance varying by task difficulty and medication state.

The evaluation of five PD patients using FScan insoles and Shimmer3 ankle accelerometers was conducted in [29]. Specifically, the authors extracted 457 features (325 pressure, 132 acceleration) using FFT and wavelet transforms. The Freeze Index (FI) ranked highest; four of the top five features were pressure-based, supporting the utility of plantar pressure in FoG detection. Another study examined 12 PD patients with L3-placed accelerometers performing FoG-inducing tasks [30]. They extracted impaired gait features (e.g., C, variability, regularity) and applied AdaBoost with pruned C4.5 trees. Accuracy reached 82.7% (patient-dependent) and 77.9% (patient-independent) with a low latency of 0.93 s, highlighting the benefit of combining personalized pre-FoG labeling with gait features. Finally, a GaitScore-based algorithm using a 6-D IMU to detect FoG vs. rest and motion phases in four PD patients was proposed in [31]. Based on pitch angle analysis, the method achieved 97% sensitivity and 87% specificity, validated against clinical video annotations.

In summary, these studies showcase significant advancements in FoG prediction and detection using wearable sensors and ML. While results are promising, with several models exceeding 90% accuracy, challenges remain, particularly in generalizing across patient variability and real-world settings. It is important to note that many of the very high accuracies reported in this subsection—frequently above 95% and in some cases approaching 99%—were obtained under constrained experimental conditions, small and homogeneous patient samples, or within-subject validation setups, all of which can artificially inflate performance and limit generalizability. Future work should prioritize larger cohorts, multimodal data integration, and deployment in natural environments to ensure broader clinical applicability.

B. GAIT EVENTS AND PHASES ESTIMATION

Gait events and phases represent critical elements of the walking cycle, and accurate estimation is particularly important in PD due to associated motor impairments such as bradykinesia, rigidity, and postural instability. These symptoms, integral to clinical assessments such as the Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS), disrupt normal gait timing and coordination, significantly affecting mobility and quality of life. Accurate identification of gait phases, such as stance and swing, and key events such as HS and TO supports diagnosis, progression monitoring, and the development of rehabilitation tools. Wearable sensors and AI algorithms now enable real-time, continuous monitoring, offering a detailed picture of motor impairments in PD.

In [32], smart glasses with IMUs were used to monitor seven PD patients during the Timed-Up-and-Go test (TUG). The system detected gait events from accelerometer data with an average error of 8.1%, and step detection showed strong correlation with the severity of PD symptoms measured by the FOG and Parkinson’s Disease Questionnaire (PDQ-8) scores. A wearable inertial Motion Capture system (MoCap) was validated against OptiTrack in 35 participants, including PD and FoG patients in [33]. Using IMUs and an Error State Kalman Filter, and analyzed via LSTM, the system reached 99.11% phase detection accuracy, showing promise for clinical applications. Similarly, wrist-worn sensors and five gait detection algorithms were compared in [34], including LSTM and CNN models. The CNN achieved the highest AUC (0.94 for older adults, 0.89 for PD), though precision-recall performance varied.

In [35], an L5-placed IMU and a Finite State Machine (FSM) algorithm with adaptive thresholds were used to detect five gait events utilizing a dataset of 20 patients with PD. Tested against Vicon MoCap and Xsens IMU systems in lab and clinical settings, it achieved sensitivity of 95.09–99.53% and accuracy of 93.64–97.42%, confirming its utility for real-world monitoring. A U-Net CNN on tri-axial acceleration from the lumbar, shin, and wrist to detect gait events in 11 participants is employed in [36]. The lumbar sensor produced the most accurate results, with intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) ≤ 0.84 , indicating strong agreement with reference systems (data from the walkway).

In [37], multiscale entropy and complexity index (CI) were analyzed in 21 PD patients and 5 controls. PD patients showed significantly higher CI under dual-task conditions ($P < 0.05$), indicating increased motor-cognitive load during walking. A pipeline using foot-worn IMUs and a HMM for real-world stair ambulation was introduced in [38]. It achieved timing errors below ± 10 ms and F1-score of 98.5% for stride segmentation, with 98.2% accuracy in stride type recognition utilizing two different datasets (one with 20 healthy and another with 13 PD patients). In [39], the authors developed a single-sensor HMM-based method to segment the gait cycle into four phases. Tested on

16 volunteers, the model reached a 91.88% recognition rate and transmitted data wirelessly to a mobile device.

An algorithmic pipeline detected standardized gait tests (such as 4×10 -meters walking test - 4×10 MWT) in 12 PD patients using Dynamic Time Warping and signal processing in [40]. The system achieved F1-scores of 88.9% for detection and 94.0% for segmenting individual walks, enhancing comparability of test data. A hybrid rule-based and linear classifier approach using IMUs on the foot in 10 subjects (6 with PD) is proposed in [41]. F1-scores were 0.974 (PD) and 0.988 (controls). A follow-up study [42] proposed deterministic and stochastic unsupervised algorithms with F1-scores above 0.95 for both groups. Lastly, the authors in [43] developed a wearable insole with 10 force sensors and an IMU to test stride detection algorithms in 32 healthy individuals and 28 PD patients. A CNN-based method achieved F1-scores of 0.938 (TUG test) and 0.944 (daily activities), outperforming Min-Max and DTW methods.

Overall, these studies on PD gait analysis are a testament to the advancements in methodologies and technologies used in the field. These include ML algorithms, DL techniques, wearable sensors, and advanced signal processing methods. These advances have the potential to improve diagnostic accuracy, monitor disease progression, and enhance patient care. However, many of the exceptionally high accuracies reported in this subsection, often approaching near-perfect gait-phases detection, were obtained under structured walking protocols, controlled laboratory conditions, and, in only a few cases, in comparisons against high-fidelity MoCap systems. Such constrained environments reduce variability and therefore do not reliably reflect performance in real-world settings. Limitations like small sample sizes, real-world validation, and disease symptom variability necessitate further research. Future studies should focus on larger, diverse populations and integrate multimodal data for scalable solutions in clinical settings worldwide.

C. GAIT SPATIOTEMPORAL PARAMETERS-BASED CORRELATION

GSTPs, such as SdL, GS, C, and SpT, are fundamental for assessing human locomotion. These metrics offer critical insights into the spatial and temporal aspects of walking and are particularly valuable in PD, where motor symptoms such as bradykinesia, postural instability, and gait disturbances manifest as reduced SdL, increased variability, and asymmetry. Comparative analyses with healthy controls (HC) have shown that spatiotemporal feature deviations can effectively track the progression of PD, guide diagnosis, and inform targeted interventions.

In [44], vertical GRF in 18 PD patients and 18 speed-matched HC were compared during linear and curvilinear walking using Pedar-X insoles. While GRF showed no significant differences, variability in TSt timing differed ($p < 0.001$), highlighting timing irregularities as potential PD markers. An insole system integrating force-sensitive

resistors (FSRs), piezoelectric sensors, and IMUs was developed in [45]. Among 30 PD patients and 30 HC, dynamic deformation features correlated most with PD severity (Spearman $r = 0.796$, AUC = 0.8444). Combining all features raised AUC to 0.9206 with 88.3% classification accuracy.

Multiscale entropy (MSE), refined composite MSE, and CI were applied to trunk acceleration data from 51 PD patients and 50 age- and speed- matched HC in [46]. PD patients exhibited significantly higher entropy, especially in the anteroposterior and mediolateral axes, suggesting MSE as a potential biomarker of gait irregularity. Harmonic distortions in upper limb swing were analyzed in [47], where 58 PD patients and 31 HC showed reduced fundamental frequency and second harmonic amplitude in the most affected arm. These distortions correlated strongly with rigidity and bradykinesia on the MDS-UPDRS III.

A smart insole detecting foot shuffling was introduced in [48]. Ten participants simulated gait and shuffling patterns; the system, combining IMU and plantar sensors, used a cubic SVM to achieve 97.8% classification accuracy and a RMSE of 0.018 s in shuffling duration estimation. Another study analyzed 108 PD patients and 88 controls, showing kinematic features like swing time variability were more informative than dynamic ones for differentiating PD gait [49]. The study supports kinematic markers like GS and StT variability as stronger predictors for early diagnosis. Stair ambulation differences between PD fallers and non-fallers were continuously examined in [50] using IMUs in 40 patients over the period of two weeks. Fallers showed up to 20% longer StT and 16% slower GS during stairs, metrics not observed in level walking, underscoring stairs as sensitive fall risk indicators.

A body sensor network for gait analysis with IMUs and an ESKF was proposed in [51]. Validated against OptiTrack (MoCap system), it achieved 2.52 cm MAE in SpL and 0.96 cm in foot clearance. ML classifiers showed gait features better generalized PD abnormalities than raw statistics. In [52], anticipatory postural adjustments (APA) were evaluated using IMUs vs. force platforms in 25 PD and 8 elderly controls. High correlation ($r = 0.99$) was observed across temporal APA markers. PD patients had prolonged APA durations, indicating impaired postural control. While, in [53], 24 PD patients were studied and results showed that forearm pronation-supination (PS) movement metrics (speed, acceleration) correlated with UPDRS scores. PS features showed potential as surrogate gait and posture markers for remote monitoring.

In [54], 14 PD and 12 HC underwent 5-meter walk tests while IMUs recorded the largest Lyapunov exponent (LLE), sample entropy (SampEn), and root mean square (RMS). All metrics differed significantly between PD and control groups and across PD subgroups, validating nonlinear analysis in gait assessment. The authors in [55] evaluated 128 participants with IMUs at L5 and shank locations. While strong

correlations were found for SdT and StT, PD patients showed lowest agreement, particularly outdoors—highlighting environment and sensor placement effects. Atypical gait cycles were investigated in [56], showing PD patients had more atypical steps (25.4% on the most-affected side) than HC (8.1–8.8%). The most common atypical cycles in PD patients were those characterized by forefoot IC (i.e., Push-Off, Flat-Foot Contact, Push-Off, Swing, and Push-Off, Swing cycles). These patterns strongly correlated with UPDRS-III, suggesting their use as biomarkers for subtle gait dysfunctions.

The Moticon insoles were used to capture a series of exercises, including free walking at varying speeds and TUG test on 7 PD and 10 HC in [57]. Of 28 gait features assessed, 10 showed significant group differences. CoP spatial distribution during static balance exercises was the most discriminative, indicating its use in everyday PD monitoring. The GaitAnalyzer algorithm using waist-mounted IMUs on 17 PD patients was presented in [58]. The system detected fall risk through deviations in tri-axial acceleration, issuing alerts when thresholds were exceeded in real time. Gait deviations were pronounced during multitasking. In [59], gait bouts (i.e., periods of continuous walking) of varying lengths were studied in 29 PD and 20 older adults. PD patients had less adaptable C and swing duration scaling across bout lengths. Shorter bouts proved more discriminative, supporting their use as digital biomarkers.

In [60], the authors proposed a discriminant analysis model using GRF and CoP data from 29 PD and 18 HC undergoing a walking test in a 25-meter corridor at their own pace. Achieving 95% accuracy, the model identified unbalanced gait as prevalent in PD, validating GRF for early-stage detection. The examination of 74 PD and 52 HC walking at various speeds was conducted in [61]. PD patients showed higher gait asymmetry and variability, especially at slow and fast speeds. DS coefficient of variation (CV) effectively distinguished PD at fast speeds, offering insights into symptom severity.

The analysis of spatiotemporal gait features remains crucial in understanding, diagnosing, and treating PD. The evolution of technology, particularly wearable devices and advanced data analysis methods, has enriched the toolkit for more refined detection and monitoring of the disease's progression. Researchers are uncovering layers of motor impairment associated with PD through enhanced gait cycle characterization, complex analytical models, and metrics, like ML and MSE. The variety of approaches, from examining walking speed effects on gait dynamics to deploying wearable technology for real-time monitoring, demonstrates the dynamic nature of research in this field. However, many of the high discriminative performances reported for GSTP-based models are tightly linked to controlled walking tasks, speed-matched comparisons, or laboratory environments that reduce natural gait variability, which may limit generalizability to free-living conditions. As

technologies and methodologies evolve, there is potential for significant breakthroughs in patient care. The challenge is to ensure these innovations are accessible and practical in clinical settings, paving the way for a transformative era in daily management of PD.

D. FALLS PREDICTION

Falls remain a significant health concern, particularly among populations with neurological disorders such as PD and stroke survivors. The ability to accurately assess and predict fall risk is crucial for developing effective intervention strategies to prevent these often-harmful incidents. Recent advancements in technology have enabled the use of IMU and other sensor-based systems to gain a deeper understanding of gait dynamics and balance, fundamental factors contributing to falls. These technologies offer a non-invasive, detailed, and real-time method for monitoring individuals in both clinical and real-world settings, potentially revolutionizing fall risk assessment and management.

A novel approach for estimating GRF using only two IMUs placed on the shanks was proposed in [62]. The hybrid method estimates gait resistance during SS and DS phases using data collected from 31 participants, including HC, PD patients, and stroke patients. IMUs recorded at 100 Hz and force-sensing shoes at 400 Hz were used for validation. The model achieved high accuracy with normalized mean absolute error (NMAE) values of $5.95\% \pm 1.32\%$ (HC), $6.09\% \pm 2.00\%$ (PD), and $5.87\% \pm 1.59\%$ (stroke). Additionally, the study introduced a dynamic balance assessment method based on GRF and kinematics to quantify fall risk. The authors in [63] explored fall risk prediction in 40 PD patients using real-world gait data from foot-worn IMUs. Participants performed unsupervised 10-meter walking tests. ML models, including RF and Gradient Boosting (GB), were applied to predict fall risk. The RF model achieved a balanced accuracy of 74.0%, sensitivity of 60.0%, and specificity of 88.0%, with the highest predictive performance obtained from aggregated gait data. Fall risk using insole-based monitoring during dual-task walking in 10 PD patients and 8 HC was examined in [64]. Insoles with embedded accelerometers at the heel and first metatarsal captured gait data under two conditions: normal walking and walking while holding a cup of water. The dual-task condition showed improved classification accuracy (82.37%) compared to normal walking (72.63%). Bayesian Ridge regression was used to estimate fall risk scores, which correlated well with the Fall Risk Questionnaire (FRQ), yielding a minimal error of 0.03 ± 0.38 .

These studies explore the use of sensor-based technologies and advanced analytical techniques to improve fall risk prediction. By integrating real-time data collection with sophisticated predictive models, researchers can provide more accurate insights into fall prevention strategies, especially in individuals with PD. The reported performance levels, such as low NMAE and moderate-to-high classification scores in

fall-risk prediction, reflect the structured testing protocols, limited cohort diversity, or aggregation of gait data used in these studies, which can constrain variability and therefore may not fully capture the complexity of fall risk in natural daily environments. Further research is needed to refine these methods and ensure their accessibility across diverse settings.

E. TURNS

Gait analysis, particularly during complex tasks like turning, offers critical insights into the functional impairments associated with PD. Turning motions, which involve dynamic shifts in balance and motor control, are particularly challenging for PD patients and are thus crucial for assessing disease impact and progression. Advances in wearable technology have enabled more precise and comprehensive monitoring of these movements, facilitating early detection and improved management of PD. The integration of IMU into everyday clinical practice and research settings allows for the detailed capture of gait parameters and turning dynamics, opening new avenues for understanding and treating this debilitating disease.

An algorithmic pipeline for automated detection and analysis of TUG tests using foot-mounted IMUs in 32 PD patients was introduced in [65]. Designed to operate without clinician supervision, the system enabled unsupervised TUG assessments in both laboratory and at-home environments. The algorithm demonstrated high sensitivity (98.6%) for TUG detection and achieved an F1-score of 89.6% using a RF classifier in cross-validation of at-home data. It also decomposed the TUG test into sub-phases, offering detailed insights into gait and balance performance in real-world conditions.

The evaluation of a spatiotemporal gait model for early-stage PD detection during turning tasks in 30 participants, including young adults, elderly adults, and PD patients was presented in [66]. The model was validated against a Vicon MoCap system, demonstrating strong correlations (Pearson's $R = 0.82$ – 0.99) and minimal bias. PD patients exhibited shorter SdL and slower walking speeds during turns, highlighting the model's effectiveness in identifying early gait impairments associated with PD. In a related study [67], turning movements in 37 PD patients and 56 healthy controls using IMU sensors were analyzed. A Kalman filter-based algorithm accurately detected turn initiation and completion, achieving an ICC of 0.99. Turning metrics—angular velocity, duration, step count, and jerk—were extracted and classified using Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (PLS-DA), yielding 97.85% accuracy, 97.5% sensitivity, and 96.43% specificity. The study emphasizes the role of precise sensor placement and multidimensional features in classifying PD-related turning deficits.

These studies indicate that IMU-based technologies can improve PD management by providing more accurate

insights into patient mobility and balance, especially during complex tasks like turning. As these technologies evolve, their integration into clinical assessments and home monitoring systems can enhance diagnosis precision and intervention efficacy. Nonetheless, several of the high performance values reported in this subsection, including strong correlations with MoCap systems, near-perfect ICCs for turn detection, and classification accuracies exceeding 95%, must be interpreted cautiously, as many studies relied on relatively small cohorts and uneven distributions of PD patients and healthy controls. Such sample characteristics increase the risk of overfitting and can inflate model accuracy by making it easier to discriminate between disproportionately represented groups rather than capturing the full variability of PD-related turning impairments. Further research and refinement are needed to ensure robustness, user-friendliness, and accessibility.

F. GAIT PATTERNS, DIAGNOSIS, AND SEVERITY

Accurately diagnosing PD and assessing its severity are pivotal for tailoring treatment strategies and managing the progression of the disease effectively. Recent advances in technology have expanded the diagnostic toolkit, allowing for more nuanced analysis of gait and motor functions—critical indicators of PD. Utilizing various sensor technologies, from foot PPS to wearable IMU, researchers are now able to capture intricate details of gait that are often imperceptible in clinical examinations. These technological interventions not only enhance the precision of PD diagnoses but also provide valuable insights into the severity and progression of the disease, facilitating early intervention and personalized care.

The application of tensor decomposition techniques on foot pressure data collected through FSRs to classify neurodegenerative diseases, including PD, Huntington's disease (HD), and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is investigated in [68]. Researchers used CANDECOMP/PARAFAC (CP) tensor decomposition on foot pressure data from 16 HC, 15 PD, 20 HD, and 13 ALS patients. Data from FSRs was processed into 3D tensors and classified using an ensemble of binary SVMs. After Z-score normalization and removal of turning/start-up segments, the method showed high classification accuracy for distinguishing neurodegenerative diseases. A wearable IoT ankle with a 3-axis accelerometer and gyroscope to grade PD severity based on Hoehn and Yahr scale was presented in [69]. Tested on 40 PD patients, the system extracted 150 features and selected 9 key features from walking sessions, achieving 96.5% accuracy with KNN, outperforming other ML models.

An adaptive Spatio-Temporal Directed Graph Neural Network (AST-DGNN) using plantar topological graphs from GRF data was proposed in [70]. Trained on three public datasets, it outperformed CNN-LSTM and Transformers by 2.13% in accuracy, 7.73% in F1, and 12.27% in G-mean. While generalization was strong, its complexity may limit real-time application. Optical flow fields from insole-based

GRF data of 93 PD and 73 HC were used to quantify gait in [71]. CART classifiers achieved 93.3% diagnostic and 91.4% severity accuracy, outperforming SVM, RF, and KNN. The method highlights the utility of spatiotemporal force mapping despite its computational demands. Two shank-mounted IMUs in 25 PD and 28 HC were utilized to estimate UPDRS gait scores with a nonlinear model in [72]. The system classified 84.9% of patients into correct UPDRS levels, outperforming SVM, Naive Bayes, and Logistic Regression. However, patients with UPDRS levels 3–4 were excluded.

In [73], PD and HC were classified using GRF signals from the PhysioNet dataset (93 PD, 73 HC). After preprocessing, four features were extracted from left–right foot differences. A Decision Tree model achieved 88% accuracy, supporting GRF's utility, though larger-scale validation is needed. The evaluation of early PD detection using IMUs embedded in shoes (30 PD, 30 HC) was presented in [74]. GSTPs were derived from these data to feed the feature selection and AI methods, while recursive feature elimination and a DT classifier yielded 91.6% accuracy, with 91% sensitivity and 83% specificity, effectively capturing subtle gait changes. The use of 1D-CNNs to GRF signals from the PhysioNet NDD dataset was explored in [75]. The method involved processing GRF signals through 1D-CNNs to extract deep features, which were then classified using ML algorithms. SVM achieved 95.2% detection accuracy, while MLP reached 82.6% for severity grading, indicating deep features' effectiveness in early-stage classification.

Another approach to analyzing gait dynamics in PD patients using plantar pressure data from five foot regions was presented in [76]. Researchers have developed a method to classify PD severity via an RBF NN. The model achieved 100% accuracy for diagnosis, 95.89% for severity grading, and 96.00% on a new dataset. Sub-regional analysis enhanced detection but may be limited with low-resolution sensors. To diagnose PD and predict its severity using a combination of static and dynamic temporal networks, the authors in [77] used GRF data from PPS in the soles of 93 PD patients and 73 HC. A model was developed using two pathways: the Static Temporal Pathway, which extracts temporal features, and the Dynamic Temporal Pathway, which captures force transfer patterns across the foot surface. The fusion of these two pathways improved the model's performance, achieving 96.7% accuracy for PD detection and 92.3% for severity prediction.

In one study [78], IMUs and strain sensors were used on five subjects to classify gait using a CNN-RNN architecture with an attention mechanism. The system achieved 98.9% accuracy, 97.8% sensitivity, and successfully detected freezing episodes in PD patients. Another approach deployed tri-axial accelerometers at the hip, knee, and ankle to classify PD severity using a kernel-based SVM [79]. The model achieved 95.31% accuracy during a 40-meter walk and 92.51% during free walking, highlighting its suitability for

continuous, cloud-based monitoring. Using smart insoles equipped with PPS and an IMU, a study involving 19 PD patients, 7 elderly, and 18 healthy controls extracted 18 spatiotemporal gait features [80]. A RF classifier achieved 88% accuracy for PD vs. healthy classification, 73% for PD vs. elderly vs. adults, and 81% for ON vs. OFF medication state classification.

A novel method utilized Petri net models to analyze transition times between gait phases using PhysioNet GRF data [81]. When applied to PD, Huntington's, and ALS patients, the RF model achieved 90.6% classification accuracy, while classification trees reached only 62.3%, emphasizing the robustness of Petri net-based features. An advanced classification system employed the eGaIT IMU system with CNN, GRU, and hybrid CNN-GRU models [82]. The CNN-GRU model achieved 83.7% accuracy distinguishing PD from elderly controls and 92.7% accuracy for PD vs. young healthy controls, demonstrating the advantages of combining temporal and spectral features. In another study, 22 trunk acceleration features were extracted from lumbar-mounted IMUs in 81 PD patients and 80 healthy subjects [83]. Among the five ML models tested, SVM, RF, and DT achieved accuracies exceeding 80%. Clinical insight-guided feature selection improved interpretability and reduced overfitting risk.

A low-power wearable network consisting of five 9-axis IMUs was introduced to monitor motor function in 17 PD patients [84]. The system captured gait spatiotemporal parameters with 87% accuracy for trajectory metrics, 90% for time-frequency features, and 95% for angular measures, enabling continuous monitoring applications. Using GRF data from Velostat-based insoles and a FlexiForce A401 sensor from two PhysioNet datasets, another method applied KNN, SVM, and RF to classify neurodegenerative diseases [85]. KNN achieved the highest performance, with classification accuracies of 99.08% and 99.95% across the two datasets.

A rapid diagnostic method employed smart insoles with 16 PPS, a tri-axis accelerometer, and gyroscope [86]. By applying time-window segmentation and statistical feature extraction, a RF model achieved 97.05% accuracy and a 97.04% F1-score in detecting PD from walking data in a 29-participant cohort. Lastly, a hybrid insole system integrating 16-channel piezoresistive and 8-channel piezoelectric sensors was developed to assess plantar pressure and deformation during gait [87]. The system effectively distinguished between PD patients and healthy individuals by identifying significant differences in pressure peaks, gait cycles, and dynamic deformations.

A wearable system using force-sensitive insoles paired with IMUs was developed to monitor abnormal gait in PD patients [88]. Involving 14 PD patients and 8 healthy controls, the system collected SdT, SpT, SwP and StP, and stepping frequency via a Bluetooth-enabled mobile application. A Gradient Boosting classifier achieved 97.31% accuracy.

TABLE 2. Selected manuscripts with analytics for Parkinson’s Disease linking sensor modality to gait features and analytic methods, including findings, protocol and cohort details.

Ref.	Modality	Gait Features	Algorithms (Type)	Key Findings	Protocol	Cohort Details
[23]	Tri-axial IMU (shank, thigh, lower back)	Freezing Index, Entropies and Frequency Bands, StD, Mean	ResNeXt, SMOTE, Manual Feature Selection (Predictive)	95.4% prediction accuracy; MF1 = 0.89, Kappa = 0.87; manual + DL features improved performance	Walked in straight hallways and rooms; turns included	10 PD patients (7 males, 3 females), all with advanced PD
[30]	Accelerometer on lower back (L3)	C, Step Variability, Step Regularity, FI, HR	AdaBoost with pruned C4.5 trees (Predictive)	82.7% accuracy, 0.93s latency; impaired gait features enhanced prediction accuracy	FoG-provoking tasks: straight walking, turning, doorway crossing; 100 Hz sampling rate	12 PD patients (5 males, mean age 70.1 years)
[34]	Wrist-worn IMU (accelerometer)	Gait Episodes, C, Speed, Regularity	DCNN, Anomaly Detection, AR-iHMM, LSTM (Predictive)	DCNN AUC: 0.94 (OAs), 0.89 (PD); AUPRC: 0.66 (OAs), 0.60 (PD)	Daily living activities, worn up to 10 days; sampled at 25 Hz (wrist), 100 Hz (lower back)	30 participants: 12 older adults, 18 PD patients
[35]	Single IMU at L5 vertebra	HS, FF, MSt, TO, HO	FSM with adaptive thresholds, motion compensation (Diagnostic)	Sensitivity: up to 99.53%, Accuracy: up to 97.42%	10-meter walk tests at various speeds; sampled at 100 Hz	30 participants: 10 healthy, 20 PD patients
[45]	FSRs, PERs, IMUs integrated in insoles	Plantar Pressure, Dynamic Deformation, Postural Angles	PCA, Spearman Correlation, ROC Analysis (Diagnostic)	Max AUC: 0.9206, Accuracy: 88.3%; deformation features highly correlated with PD severity	30-meter corridor walk; data collected at 1000 Hz	60 participants: 30 PD patients, 30 healthy controls
[46]	MIMU on lower back (L5)	Trunk Acceleration (AP, ML, V), Gait Complexity, Gait Variability	MSE, RCMSE, CI (Descriptive)	MSEAP τ_4/τ_5 and MSEML τ_4 best discriminators; PTP+ = 79–82%; correlated with motor disability	30-meter walk at self-selected pace; sampled at 100 Hz; entropy-based analysis	101 participants: 51 PD, 50 HC (age- and speed-matched)
[57]	Moticon [®] insoles with 16 pressure sensors, 6-axis IMU	Spatial CoP, Gait Cycle Time, Double/Single Support Time	Statistical Analysis, Information Gain, Chi-square test (Descriptive)	Spatial CoP distribution most discriminative; 10 significant gait features identified	10m walking at various speeds, TUG test, static balance test; sampled at 100 Hz	17 participants: 7 PD patients, 10 healthy controls
[62]	IMUs on shanks, Force-sensing shoes	GRF, COP, COM	Newton-Euler Equations, Elastic Elements Model, DBSCAN (Diagnostic)	NMAE: 5.95%±1.32% (HC), 6.09%±2.00% (PD), 5.87%±1.59% (stroke); novel GRF-based balance assessment	Walked 10-meter path, 3 trials; data sampled at 100 Hz (IMUs), 400 Hz (shoes)	31 participants: 10 HC, 11 PD, 10 stroke patients
[65]	Foot-mounted IMUs on instep	Gait Phases, Turn 180, Turn to Sit, Angular Velocity, Linear Acceleration	RF, SVM, NB (Predictive)	98.6% sensitivity, F1-score 89.6% for TUG detection; effective sub-phase decomposition	TUG test on 3-meter path; data sampled at 102.4 Hz	32 PD patients (mean age 64.2 years)
[69]	IoT anklets with 3-axis accelerometer and gyroscope	Pitch, Yaw, Roll Angles; Step Frequency; Stride, Stance, SwT; Stance Ratio	Optimized KNN, SVM, NB, DT, QDA (Diagnostic)	Accuracy: 96.5%; outperformed other ML models by $\geq 1\%$	Two 15-meter corridor walks; data collected at 50 Hz	40 PD patients (grades 1–3); avg. age 67 years
[71]	Pressure sensors in insoles	vGRF, Optical Flow Fields, Gait Symmetry, GSTPs	CART, RF, SVM, KNN, Naive Bayes (Predictive)	93.3% accuracy in PD diagnosis, 91.4% in severity assessment; CART outperformed others	Walk on flat ground for 2 minutes at natural speed; data sampled at 100 Hz	166 participants: 93 PD patients, 73 healthy controls
[72]	Shank-mounted IMUs	SdL, Gait Cycle Duration, SwP %, Max Ankle Height, Lateral Displacement, Max Ankle Velocity	Nonlinear Model, SVM, Naive Bayes, Linear Regression (Predictive)	Nonlinear model: 84.9% accuracy; outperformed SVM/Naive Bayes (73.6%)	12+ meter straight walk; data collected at 100 Hz	53 participants: 25 PD patients, 28 healthy controls
[74]	IMUs embedded in sampling shoes	SdL, StT, SwP Variability, Step Speed, C	DT with RFE (Predictive)	DT: 91.6% accuracy, 91% sensitivity, 83% specificity in classifying EPD	Six gait cycles in straight-line walk; sampled at 100 Hz	60 participants: 30 EPD patients, 30 healthy controls

IMU: Inertial Measurement Unit, FSR: Force Sensitive Resistor, PER: Piezoelectric Sensor, StD: Standard Deviation, C: Cadence, FI: Freezing Index, HS: Heel Strike, FF: Flat Foot, MSt: Mid Stance, TO: Toe Off, HO: Heel off, CoP: Center of Pressure, CoM: Center of Mass, SwT: Swing Time, vGRF: vertical Ground Reaction Forces, GSTPs: Gait Spatiotemporal Parameters, SdL: Stride Length, SwP%: Swing Phase in Percentage, StT: Stance Time

Limitations included small sample size and constrained environments. Unsupervised learning was applied to plantar bend data from Polyvinylidene Fluoride cantilever sensors embedded in insoles to detect early-stage PD [89]. Gait features such as SwP, StP, gait cycle, and DS were extracted from 6 healthy and 2 PD participants. Clustering based on coefficient of variation and asymmetry index achieved an Adjusted Rand Index of 1, effectively separating PD from control gait patterns.

To quantify PD severity, a hybrid CNN and Locally Weighted RF model was trained on gait data collected via GRF sensors from 93 PD and 73 control subjects [90]. The model predicted UPDRS scores with a correlation coefficient of 0.897 and a mean absolute error of 3.009. Classification accuracy reached 99.5%, with sensitivity and specificity of 98.7% and 99.1%, respectively. A smart insole integrated with mist computing architecture was developed for real-time gait analysis in PD patients [91]. Using embedded PPS and IMUs, gait features like C, SdL, and symmetry were captured and analyzed locally to reduce cloud processing latency.

The system was tested on 20 participants including PD patients and healthy individuals. In a pilot study, ML techniques were used to classify four gait cycle phases, flat foot, heel rise, toe off, and heel strike, from 13 subjects [92]. Gait data collected under varied walking speeds yielded 25 raw features. Among SVM, KNN, and MLP classifiers, MLP with more than eight hidden nodes achieved over 94% accuracy.

A real-time assessment system combining foot PPS with an attention-based bi-directional RNN was developed for PD gait monitoring [93]. Using data from two public gait datasets, the system computed a personalized gait normality score, aiding clinical assessments and EHR integration. The approach effectively distinguished between normal and abnormal gait in PD. Another method leveraged time-varying singular value decomposition (TSVD) of GRF signals to detect and stage PD [94]. Data from 93 PD and 73 control subjects across three datasets were decomposed into inter-limb time-varying singular values (ITSVs). Classification accuracy reached 97.22% for PD detection and 95.59% for staging. Gait data from 200 PD patients and 100 healthy controls were collected using a set of wearable sensors placed across the torso and limbs during TUG tests [95]. Ninety-five features were extracted, with Recursive Feature Elimination improving SVM classification to 96.67% accuracy, 96.77% sensitivity, and 96.55% specificity.

A gait dataset targeting PD, elderly individuals, and healthy adults was introduced using Moticon insoles with 16 PPS and a 6-axis IMU [96]. 29 Participants performed Walk Straight and Turn and modified TUG tests. Extracted GSTPs included SpL and support times, providing a valuable resource for gait algorithm development. A wearable system using a six-axis accelerometer transmitted gait data via Bluetooth to a server, where a 1D CNN classified the signals into normal or PD-related patterns such as FOG and panic

gait [97]. Tested on 50 PD and 50 controls, the system achieved 91.4% accuracy with 5-fold cross-validation.

Causal decomposition of bilateral GRF signals was applied to understand gait dynamics in 93 PD and 73 healthy individuals walking at a self-selected pace [98]. Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition and phase dependency metrics revealed frequency-specific causal interactions correlating with PD progression. To classify PD, ALS, and HD using gait signals, Recurrence Quantification Analysis (RQA) was applied to a neurodegenerative gait database (13 subjects with each disease and 13 HC) [99]. RQA features were optimized using hill-climbing and classified via SVM and Probabilistic NN, achieving up to 100% accuracy across binary classification tasks. In a similar vein, GRF data from the PhysioNet database were segmented and transformed into recurrence plots, then analyzed via PCA and classified using a CNN model [100]. In a multiclass setting (HC, ALS, PD, HD), classification accuracies exceeded 96%, with binary comparisons achieving up to 100%.

A dual-shank IMU pipeline was used to extract eight GSTPs and kinematic parameters such as ankle velocity and gait cycle duration from 49 participants with PD, stroke, peripheral neuropathy, and controls [101]. SVM classification with majority voting reached 93.9% accuracy. Lower-back accelerometry from 142 participants (81 PD, 61 control) enabled extraction of 210 gait features across multiple domains [102]. Signal-based metrics like RMS, PSD, and harmonic ratios yielded superior classification in PLS-DA models, with the top model achieving 88.73% accuracy, 90.12% sensitivity and 86.89% specificity. A deep learning framework named DCALSTM was proposed to classify PD using GRF signals from 93 PD and 73 healthy subjects [103]. Combining CNN with attention-enhanced LSTM, the model independently analyzed left and right gait asymmetries. It achieved 99.31% diagnostic accuracy and 99.01% for severity level classification.

The integration of advanced sensor technologies and AI techniques in the studies discussed above provides a compelling glimpse into the future of PD diagnosis and severity assessment. By harnessing the power of detailed gait analysis, these approaches offer a substantial improvement over traditional clinical evaluations, detecting subtle disruptions in motor function that may otherwise go unnoticed. However, many of the exceptionally high diagnostic and severity-classification accuracies reported in this body of work must be interpreted with caution. These results are frequently derived from relatively small or demographically imbalanced cohorts, where healthy controls outnumber PD participants, increasing the risk of overfitting and biasing models toward easier between-group distinctions. Moreover, most studies rely on structured laboratory tasks, speed-matched comparisons, or curated public datasets, conditions that substantially reduce gait variability and may inflate performance relative to real-world clinical environments. Limited external or multi-center validation further restricts

generalizability, underscoring the need for larger, more diverse populations and standardized evaluation frameworks. Continued progress will depend on translating these promising findings into robust, scalable, and clinically deployable systems capable of operating reliably across heterogeneous patient populations and daily-life contexts.

VI. RESEARCH TRENDS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This section synthesizes the findings presented in the previous sections into high-level insights to uncover cross-cutting trends in sensor-based gait analytics. It aims to identify patterns in sensor placement strategies, algorithmic approaches, and disorder-specific focus areas to facilitate digestible, actionable conclusions for researchers and clinicians, along with future directions. Fig. 3 presents an overview of the identified challenges in portable sensor-based gait analysis, along with the corresponding future directions proposed to address them.

Beyond these challenges, an additional trend emerges from the distribution of studies included in this review: among the 97 studies, 81 focused on PD (i.e., 83.5%), 12 on Diabetes Mellitus (i.e., 12.4%), and only 4 on Arthritis (i.e., 4.1%). This distribution was not intentional in the review design, which aimed to represent three major disorder categories: neurodegenerative, musculoskeletal, and metabolic with peripheral involvement, but rather reflects the current broader research landscape. The high representation of PD-related studies is likely driven by multiple factors, including but not limited to the well-defined motor symptoms of PD, the suitability of gait-based biomarkers for disease monitoring, and the established utility of wearable sensors, such as IMUs and PPS in capturing these features.

Given this imbalance, it is important to highlight that Diabetes Mellitus and Arthritis remain significantly underexplored despite their substantial gait-related burden. To address this gap, a dedicated subsection is included that expands on the specific deficiencies observed in these two domains, including the lack of publicly available datasets, under-defined gait tasks, insufficient bedside-ready sensor solutions, and limited translational deployment. It also outlines a concrete research blueprint detailing recommended sample sizes, sensor placements, task designs, clinically meaningful gait endpoints, and ML evaluation strategies. Collectively, a forward-looking framework is provided to guide future research and improve methodological and clinical consistency in these underrepresented motor-impaired populations.

A. SENSOR PLACEMENT PATTERNS PER ANALYTICAL OBJECTIVE

Across the reviewed literature, sensor placement emerges as a crucial design decision in gait analytics, closely aligned with the analytical objective, target disorder, and the nature of the data being collected. While a wide range of configurations was observed, certain patterns consistently

recurred within and across disease groups, reflecting both technical preferences and clinical priorities.

In studies addressing Diabetes Mellitus, foot-based sensor placements, such as plantar pressure mats and in-shoe pressure insoles, were most frequently used in diagnostic and descriptive-associative tasks (7 out of 12 studies). These devices captured detailed spatiotemporal and load-distribution metrics, enabling early identification of ulceration risk and biomechanical abnormalities, especially in patients with or without peripheral neuropathy. Peak plantar pressure at the metatarsal heads and midfoot was often highlighted as a predictive marker, with specific thresholds linked to DFU history. On the other hand, lower-back IMUs (i.e., L4 and L5) were used to assess global gait characteristics, including stride length, cadence, and gait variability in 3 out of 12 studies. These sensors proved valuable in associating gait abnormalities with sensory impairments, supporting their role in early screening and longitudinal monitoring. Multi-site IMU setups, typically including hip, knee, and ankle placements, were used in 2 out of 12 deep learning-driven studies, achieving over 90% classification accuracy in distinguishing diabetic from non-diabetic gait. These configurations enabled raw time-series inputs to be fed into CNNs or LSTMs, favoring high-resolution diagnostic tasks where spatial granularity was essential.

A somewhat parallel pattern appears in Arthritis-related research, where foot-mounted sensors again dominated, albeit with different clinical goals. In this context, pressure and piezoresistive insoles were applied to assess pain states, load asymmetries, or to enable real-time rehabilitative feedback in 2 out of 4 studies. One of those studies using a piezoresistive insole sensors achieved 99.44% accuracy in detecting knee pain using a KNN model, while the other employed a piezoelectric plate to dynamically control vibration feedback in a knee orthosis based on foot pressure, paving the way for personalized, low-cost physiotherapy. For broader assessments of gait mechanics and variability, particularly in PsA, researchers employed multi-point IMU configurations spanning the chest, lumbar spine, wrists, and feet. These allowed fine-grained tracking of cadence, double support time, and stride time variability, with significant differences observed between PsA patients and healthy controls. Similarly, in JIA, knee-mounted accelerometers captured reductions in range of motion (ROM) with promising alignment to clinical findings, highlighting the value of joint-specific monitoring. Thus, foot sensors served as effective tools for real-time feedback and pain inference, while segment-specific IMUs were better suited for functional assessments and joint monitoring.

In the context of PD, sensor placement is notably more specialized and diverse, tailored to the complexity of motor symptoms and the high variability in clinical tasks. For high-temporal-resolution applications like FoG detection (9 studies) or gait phase segmentation (12 studies), multi-IMU arrays, typically positioned on the ankles, thighs, and lower back, were most effective (8 out of 9 FOG studies,

FIGURE 3. The identified challenges and proposed future directions.

10 out of 12 gait phases studies). These configurations, often combined with CNNs, LSTMs, or hybrid architectures, enabled extraction of deep temporal features such as Freezing Index and entropy measures, achieving predictive accuracies well above 95%. Foot or lumbar placements alone were also found effective for phase estimation using FSMs or HMMs, offering a favorable balance between data fidelity and wearability. For broader diagnostic and severity estimation tasks (36 studies), pressure insoles or foot-based IMUs, often complemented by sensors on the lower back, captured global gait dynamics such as stride variability and cadence asymmetry (33 out of 36 studies). These placements fed into both classical (e.g., SVM, RF) and deep learning pipelines, with several models reaching almost perfect classification accuracies when trained on multimodal data.

Taken together, the reviewed studies suggest that no single sensor placement serves all objectives; rather, optimal placement is highly context-dependent. Foot-mounted sensors are consistently favored for detecting local anomalies, pain-related adaptations, and plantar pressure shifts across all three disorders. Lumbar or lower-back IMUs serve well in capturing global gait characteristics and progression markers, particularly in PD and Diabetes. More complex, multi-site configurations are generally reserved for deep learning tasks that require rich spatial and temporal detail. This stratification of placement strategies reflects an emerging best practice: aligning sensor configuration not just with disease type, but with the specific functional or clinical goal at hand.

B. MACHINE LEARNING AND DEEP LEARNING PERFORMANCE ACROSS TASKS

A total of 49 studies (i.e., 50.5% of the review set) across Parkinson's Disease, Diabetes Mellitus, and Arthritis employed AI methods for gait analytics. Among these, 34 studies used conventional ML approaches, while 15 implemented DL frameworks. These models were applied across a diverse set of clinical objectives including disease classification, symptom severity prediction, gait event segmentation, and therapeutic feedback systems. Please note that some articles implemented multiple AI algorithms, so the percentages following do not sum to 100%.

Random Forests, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Support Vector Machines were each used once in diabetes (4 studies) and arthritis (1 study) studies while Random Forests (55.8%), Support Vector Machines (52.9%) and Decision Trees (29.4%) were utilised in PD studies, where handcrafted features, such as stride length, cadence, plantar pressure patterns, and joint range of motion, were explicitly extracted and selected. These models were particularly effective when working with PPS data, achieving high diagnostic accuracy (up to 99.4%) in tasks like diabetic gait classification or arthritis pain detection using pressure-based heatmaps. In contrast, IMU data, especially from the lumbar spine or lower limbs, supported both handcrafted and learning-based pipelines, particularly in large-scale studies examining gait correlations with sensory deficits or cognitive decline.

In the case of PD, CNNs (66.6%) and LSTM (13.3%) models were the dominant deep learning approaches, especially in applications like FoG prediction, fall risk assessment, and medication state monitoring. These models leveraged raw IMU signals from multi-sensor configurations (e.g., shank, thigh, lower back), allowing for the automatic extraction of temporal dynamics, phase transitions, and non-linear gait patterns. Hybrid architectures that combined domain-specific handcrafted features (e.g., Freezing Index, stride variability) with deep representations (e.g., ResNeXt or CNN-LSTM) often achieved the highest reported performance, up to 100% classification accuracy, particularly in FoG prediction or PD diagnosis.

A comparative evaluation of ML and DL methods across studies revealed that ML models tend to outperform DL when working with small, structured datasets, especially those reliant on pressure-based inputs or clinically interpretable features. On the other hand, end-to-end DL approaches, fed directly with raw time-series IMU data, excelled in high-resolution, temporally dense tasks, particularly in Parkinson's-focused applications. Notably, IMU-based systems were more commonly paired with DL pipelines due to their ability to provide rich, multi-axial motion data, while PPS-based systems lent themselves well to ML models and handcrafted feature workflows due to their static, spatially grounded outputs.

These motifs underscore that algorithmic performance is highly dependent on both sensor type and feature strategy. Handcrafted ML pipelines offer strong interpretability and clinical feasibility in structured settings, particularly for diabetes and arthritis, while DL approaches are well-suited for complex, high-temporal-resolution tasks in Parkinson's Disease; but only when sufficient data volume is available. Future research may benefit from combining both paradigms, leveraging the strengths of handcrafted features and deep embeddings in hybrid models tailored to the specific disorder and objective at hand.

C. DATA COLLECTION PROTOCOLS AND STUDY DESIGN

Gait analysis studies across the reviewed diseases exhibit substantial variability in their data collection protocols, reflecting differences in clinical aims, sensor types, and participant capabilities. While such diversity enables broad applicability, it also introduces challenges in terms of reproducibility, inter-study comparability, and the real-world generalizability of findings.

Most studies conducted trials in controlled indoor environments, such as hospital corridors, gait labs, or research clinics. These settings allowed for precise sensor calibration, noise reduction, and repeatable conditions, favorable for validating algorithms and comparing intervention effects. However, they may not fully capture the variability of real-world gait, especially in PD, where symptoms like FoG often occur unpredictably outside clinical observation. One study explicitly included outdoor walking conditions, with findings including that gait variability was highest in outdoor settings

that underscore the need for further research in real-world contexts. Therefore, gait analysis algorithms may perform differently depending on environment. Beyond this, only a handful of studies, particularly those employing wearable IMUs, extended data collection to unsupervised or semi-natural settings, which are better suited for assessing gait under ecological conditions but introduce variability that complicates modeling.

Protocol designs also varied significantly in walking distances and task complexity. Common setups included one or multiple 10-meter walk tests (28.8%), often including a 180-degree turn, or its equivalent measured through gait cycles or fixed duration trials (e.g., 2-minute walks) conducted on pressure mats or insoles. These short-distance tests were most frequently used in PD and Arthritis studies to evaluate motor transitions (e.g., sit-to-stand, turns, initiation). In Diabetes-related work, straight-line walking over flat surfaces was most prevalent (83.3%), with pressure mapping focused on identifying high-risk foot zones. A few studies went beyond linear walks, incorporating dual-tasking, stair navigation, or flexion-extension movements, especially in Arthritis cohorts and PD patients at risk of falling.

Sensor setups also impacted protocol choices. Foot-based pressure systems often required barefoot or standardized footwear use over short, repeated trials, whereas IMU-based studies allowed more flexible walking paths and greater motion range, sometimes including 180-degree turning, pausing, or multiple laps. Studies employing multi-sensor arrays often designed segmented walking tasks to synchronize data streams and assess different phases of gait (e.g., initiation, steady-state, turn, stop).

Therefore, while standardized clinical tests improve internal consistency, they may overlook critical variability in gait expression. Conversely, real-world protocols offer ecological validity but introduce noise and inconsistencies. For future work, hybrid protocols that combine structured tasks with free walking, and transparent reporting of conditions (e.g., flooring, lighting, footwear), would enhance both replicability and real-world relevance of gait analytics systems.

D. COHORT CHARACTERISTICS AND SAMPLING BIAS

The demographic composition and sampling strategies used across these studies vary considerably, often reflecting the disorder under investigation and the availability of clinical populations. PD studies tended to include relatively homogeneous cohorts, typically adults in early to moderate stages of the disease, with tightly controlled age ranges and often limited gender diversity. Furthermore, age- and/or speed-matched control groups were included in only 7.4% of the studies, highlighting a potential limitation in cohort balancing strategies. Participant cohort sizes in the reviewed PD studies were distributed as follows: 34 out of 81 studies (42.0%) included 4–30 participants, 28 studies (34.6%) involved 31–100 participants, and 19 studies (23.4%) featured more

than 100 participants. While the homogeneity benefits algorithmic training and reduces within-group variability, it risks overlooking important motor differences across age groups, disease stages, or underrepresented populations. In contrast, diabetes-related studies included larger and more demographically diverse samples, sometimes exceeding 1,000 participants. These studies often stratified subjects by the presence of diabetic complications (e.g., peripheral neuropathy), although imbalance in group sizes (e.g., fewer healthy controls or ulcer-free subgroups) remained a limitation. Arthritis studies, particularly those involving JIA or PsA, frequently operated with small sample sizes (often fewer than 25 participants per group), making statistical generalization difficult despite detailed instrumentation and carefully designed protocols.

A notable pattern across all disorder groups was the underrepresentation of high-risk or advanced-condition individuals, either due to recruitment challenges, fall risk concerns, or protocol demands that required independent ambulation. This skews the data toward more mobile, cooperative patients and may diminish the real-world applicability of algorithms, especially those targeting fall prediction or gait deterioration. In PD studies, for example, severe-stage patients or those with cognitive impairment were rarely included, even though their gait dysfunction is most clinically relevant. Similarly, in diabetes, many studies excluded individuals with active foot ulcers, thereby avoiding complications during testing but also omitting valuable use cases for pressure-based risk assessment. Some arthritis studies included only unilateral joint involvement or focused on mild pain conditions, limiting the generalization to patients with polyarthritis or more complex biomechanical adaptations.

Gender representation was another recurring imbalance. While diabetes and PD studies often aimed for a balanced male-to-female ratio, several arthritis and neural network-based PD datasets skewed heavily toward one gender, often due to convenience sampling or recruitment through specialized clinics. Additionally, very few studies included younger adults or pediatric patients, despite their relevance in diseases like JIA, or stratified performance results by age group. Only a limited subset of studies explicitly addressed these biases or tested model robustness across age, sex, or disease subgroups. As gait analytics moves toward real-world deployment, addressing sampling bias and embracing demographic diversity will be essential, not only for ethical and clinical equity, but also for the reliability and generalizability of AI-based models trained on wearable sensor data.

E. BENCHMARKING AND DATASET AVAILABILITY

A key challenge observed across the reviewed studies is the lack of standardized benchmarking datasets, which significantly limits the comparability of algorithmic performance across studies, sensor configurations, and disease contexts. This issue is especially pronounced in diabetes

and arthritis, where no public, large-scale gait datasets using wearable sensors are widely referenced. Most studies in these areas rely on proprietary datasets, often collected in-house under highly specific conditions, with small-to-moderate sample sizes and limited metadata. Consequently, while the findings within individual studies may be strong, their generalizability and replicability are often uncertain. Even when statistical results are robust, the absence of shared data inhibits meaningful cross-validation of ML and deep learning models.

By contrast, in the context of PD, a few publicly available datasets such as Daphnet Freezing of Gait Dataset and parts of the PhysioNet Gait in Neurodegenerative Disease database were utilized in multiple studies. These datasets support benchmarking for specific tasks like FoG detection and allow researchers to compare their models under consistent conditions. However, even in PD, the scope remains narrow—most benchmark datasets are limited to specific tasks, sensor configurations (e.g., IMUs only), and early-stage patients. Very few studies report standardized preprocessing pipelines, let alone open-source code for reproducibility, making it difficult to assess how much performance gain stems from modeling innovation versus dataset-specific characteristics.

Another noteworthy gap is the lack of unified evaluation metrics and reporting standards. Studies often report accuracy, F1 score, sensitivity, or AUC, but these are used inconsistently, and few adopt rigorous cross-validation or external test sets. This inconsistency, coupled with the lack of common datasets, hinders fair comparison across models—even when tackling similar classification problems. To address this, future research should prioritize open data sharing, standardized evaluation benchmarks, and transparent algorithm reporting. Encouraging collaborative initiatives across institutions to develop and maintain annotated, multimodal gait datasets—especially for underrepresented disorders like arthritis—will be crucial to advancing the field toward reproducible, clinically deployable solutions.

F. CLINICAL TRANSLATION, INTERPRETABILITY, AND CLINICAL PATHWAYS

While wearable sensor-based gait analytics shows strong potential across Parkinson's Disease, Diabetes Mellitus, and Arthritis, its translation into clinical practice remains limited. Many high-performing models, especially DL architectures used in PD studies, lack transparency in how decisions are made, raising concerns about interpretability for clinicians. In contrast, traditional ML models, often used in diabetes and arthritis research, offer greater explainability through feature importance metrics and rule-based logic, making them more suitable for integration into clinical workflows. However, these models can underperform in complex, high-dimensional tasks such as medication state prediction or FoG detection. The trade-off between performance and interpretability remains a central

barrier to adoption, especially in contexts where clinicians require clear, justifiable reasoning behind AI-generated outputs.

Another challenge is the limited real-world deployment of these systems beyond controlled research environments. Few studies validate their models in longitudinal clinical trials or deploy them in home-based monitoring settings. Hardware constraints, battery life, calibration requirements, and data privacy regulations also hinder continuous monitoring at scale. Moreover, the lack of clinician-in-the-loop design, where healthcare professionals help define meaningful thresholds or interpret outputs, can result in misalignment between algorithmic outputs and clinical decision-making needs. Bridging this gap will require not just technical refinement, but also the development of intuitive interfaces, clear risk thresholds, and hybrid models that integrate both clinician knowledge and sensor-driven data to support trust, adoption, and actionability in clinical settings.

To address these gaps, wearable gait systems must provide clinically interpretable outputs that directly align with standard scales and actionable thresholds. For instance, fall-risk assessment models can map step-time variability or stride-to-stride fluctuation directly to validated clinical cutoffs (e.g., TUG > 13.5 s indicating elevated fall risk, or step-time variability $\geq 4\text{--}5\%$ used in geriatric fall prediction). Additionally, GSTP-based monitoring systems can generate early warnings when clinically meaningful changes occur, such as sudden reductions in stride length, increased stride-time variability, or diminished harmonic ratios that exceed established fall-risk benchmarks, allowing clinicians to detect deterioration before adverse events occur. Similarly, FoG detection systems can anchor sensor-derived freezing episodes to MDS-UPDRS Part III FoG item scoring or FoG-Q frequency categories, enabling clinicians to interpret alerts in terms of recognized symptom severity levels.

In metabolic impairments such as diabetic neuropathy, plantar-pressure asymmetry, peak-pressure redistribution, or stance-time imbalance can be linked to established neuropathy scales (e.g., vibration perception threshold or Michigan Neuropathy Screening Instrument categories), providing interpretable markers of sensory loss progression. For ulceration-risk monitoring, systems can prompt alerts when peak plantar pressure, pressure-time integrals, or SPPP exceed clinically recognized DFU-risk thresholds, enabling early intervention and tracking of worsening plantar-loading patterns. In arthritis-related gait disturbances, load-distribution asymmetry and prolonged stance time on the contralateral limb can be mapped to WOMAC [104] or gait-compensation scoring frameworks, supporting objective monitoring of pain-related compensatory strategies.

Implementation pathways must also emphasize how thresholds lead to clinician action. For instance, a fall-risk model could generate tiered alerts (i.e., low/moderate/high risk) calibrated to physiotherapy referral thresholds, while FoG alerts could trigger medication review or cueing

strategies once validated frequency thresholds are exceeded. For disease-severity estimation in PD, wearable-derived gait metrics, such as reduced swing-phase symmetry, increased gait variability, or diminished harmonic ratios, can be mapped to MDS-UPDRS Part III motor bradykinesia and gait-related items, enabling continuous and interpretable severity tracking aligned with established neurological scoring. Hybrid interpretable models, combining transparent features such as gait variability indices with deep-learning-derived patterns, may allow sensor systems to present both a prediction and the underlying rationale, supporting clinician trust and enabling integration with standard clinical assessments.

G. INTEROPERABILITY AND SYSTEM SCALABILITY

As gait analysis technologies evolve from research prototypes to real-world tools, interoperability and scalability emerge as critical factors potentially determining long-term impact. The reviewed studies often relied on proprietary sensor systems, custom-built preprocessing pipelines, and application-specific software—limiting their compatibility with other platforms or integration into existing clinical systems. In particular, IMUs and PPS used across Parkinson's, diabetes, and arthritis studies produced data in diverse formats with varying sampling rates, units, and structures. Without standardized data schemas or unified APIs, combining datasets, comparing models, or extending solutions across institutions becomes a major barrier. Moreover, few studies addressed how these systems could interface with electronic health records or be deployed across multi-site healthcare networks.

Scalability is also constrained by the hardware demands and data processing infrastructure required for real-time or continuous monitoring. While some wearable systems (e.g., insoles or lumbar IMUs) are lightweight and relatively non-intrusive, multi-sensor configurations involving hips, knees, and shanks can become burdensome in daily settings, especially for elderly or mobility-impaired individuals. Furthermore, deep learning pipelines with high computational requirements are typically processed offline, making real-time feedback or remote monitoring difficult without cloud-based solutions. Yet, cloud deployment introduces additional concerns related to latency, connectivity, and patient data privacy. To enable scalable and interoperable gait analytics systems, future development must prioritize modular hardware design, data standardization, and interoperable software platforms that support secure, distributed deployment across diverse clinical and home environments.

H. ETHICAL AND PRIVACY CONSIDERATIONS

As wearable gait analysis systems advance toward clinical and at-home deployment, they introduce critical ethical and privacy concerns that must be addressed alongside technical innovation. Continuous data collection, often involving accelerometry, gyroscopic signals, or pressure mapping, can inadvertently capture sensitive biometric patterns, movement habits, and even indirect health status indicators.

In many reviewed studies, particularly those using IMUs in Parkinson's or pressure insoles in diabetes, participant consent was obtained, but long-term data governance, anonymization, and secondary data use were rarely discussed. Additionally, no paper outlined how patient data security would be ensured during wireless transmission, cloud storage, or third-party analysis. This oversight is especially problematic as these systems move into more real-world, unmonitored environments where data exposure risks are amplified.

Another significant ethical consideration relates to algorithmic fairness and clinical equity. Many ML models were trained on relatively homogeneous datasets, skewed toward specific age groups, genders, or disease stages, without subgroup analysis or external validation. This raises the risk of biased model performance, particularly for underrepresented populations such as women with PD, younger arthritis patients, or rural diabetic populations with different gait adaptations. Furthermore, deep learning models with opaque decision-making processes complicate clinical trust and informed consent, as patients and clinicians may be unable to fully interpret how decisions (e.g., fall risk or symptom progression) are made. Ensuring ethical deployment, particularly in the EU AI ACT era, will require not just technical safeguards, but also transparent reporting, stakeholder involvement, and regulatory alignment to balance data utility, privacy, and fairness in the adoption of AI-driven gait analytics.

I. GAPS AND RESEARCH BLUEPRINT FOR DIABETES MELLITUS AND ARTHRITIS

Compared with PD, the research landscape for Diabetes Mellitus and Arthritis remains markedly underdeveloped. The limited number of studies identified in this review highlights several key gaps. First, no publicly available datasets exist for either disorder, restricting benchmarking, reproducibility, and the development of robust ML models. Second, the tasks used across studies are heterogeneous and often under-defined; standardized protocols targeting clinically relevant gait behaviors, such as uneven-surface or prolonged walking in neuropathic diabetes, and load-bearing or stair-climbing tasks in knee or hip arthritis, are largely absent. Third, bedside and real-world applicability remain limited: current systems rarely account for pain-related variability, footwear constraints, joint-specific compensatory strategies, or the need for simple setup in busy clinical environments. As a result, the translational potential of gait analytics for peripheral nerve and musculoskeletal disorders is not yet fully realized.

To address these gaps, future investigations in Diabetes Mellitus and Arthritis would benefit from a more structured study blueprint. We recommend prospective studies with at least 40–60 participants per clinical group (disease and matched controls), with additional stratification by disease severity or complication burden (e.g., neuropathy grade in diabetes, radiographic or clinical severity in arthritis).

Sensor configurations should prioritize feasible and clinically acceptable placements, such as a single IMU at the lower back (L5), bilateral shank sensors, and/or instrumented insoles or plantar-pressure insoles, balancing richness of data with comfort and ease of use. Standardized protocols should include both short-distance laboratory tests (e.g., 10m walk at self-selected and fast walking speeds, repeated sit-to-stand, and turning tasks) and longer-duration or semi-structured walks (e.g., 6-minute walk or real-world monitoring over several hours) to capture context-dependent gait fluctuations. Core endpoints should encompass gait speed, stride length and variability, symmetry indices, plantar-pressure redistribution patterns, double-support time, instability or freezing-like episodes, where relevant, and disease-specific clinical scales (e.g., neuropathy, pain, or joint function scores). From an analytical perspective, ML pipelines should be trained and evaluated using clearly defined data splits (e.g., subject-wise train/validation/test partitions) and stratified k -fold cross-validation, reporting metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, sensitivity, specificity, and area under the ROC curve, together with confidence intervals and appropriate handling of class imbalance. Whenever possible, external validation on an independent cohort or across institutions should be performed to assess generalizability. Adopting such a rigorous and standardized framework can accelerate the development of clinically actionable digital biomarkers and support the deployment of wearable gait analytics for Diabetes Mellitus and Arthritis in both bedside and real-world settings.

VII. DISCUSSION

This systematic review highlights the transformative potential of gait analytics in the diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment of motor disorders using wearable and portable sensing technologies, particularly IMUs and PPS. These tools have proven effective in capturing critical spatiotemporal gait parameters across diverse clinical conditions such as diabetes mellitus, arthritis, and Parkinson's disease—chosen to represent a broad spectrum of neurological, muscular, and skeletal impairments. However, the review also exposes key limitations and future research priorities.

The integration of wearable sensors with AI has enabled continuous, real-time gait monitoring in both clinical and natural settings. In diabetes, these technologies can detect early gait deviations predictive of complications like foot ulcers. In arthritis, gait analytics quantifies joint dysfunction and evaluates therapy outcomes. In Parkinson's disease, sensor-based analysis helps detect hallmark abnormalities such as freezing of gait and altered phase dynamics, supporting personalized interventions.

Yet despite these advances, challenges remain. Generalization across populations is hindered by small sample sizes, uneven distributions between healthy and diseased cohorts, limited external validation, and dependency on sensor accuracy and algorithm performance, all of which restrict the robustness and reproducibility of model

TABLE 3. List of abbreviations.

Abbrev.	Definition	Abbrev.	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence	ALS	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
APA	Anticipatory Postural Adjustment	AR-iHMM	Auto-Regressive Infinite HMM
AST-DGNN	Adaptive Spatio-Temporal Directed Graph Neural Network	AUC	Area Under the Curve
AUPRC	Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve	C	Cadence
CI	Complexity Index	CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CoM	Center of Mass	CoP	Center of Pressure
CP	Candecomp/Parafac Tensor Decomposition	CT	Computed Tomography
CV	Coefficient of Variation	DFU	Diabetic Foot Ulcer
DL	Deep Learning	DPN	Diabetes Mellitus with Peripheral Neuropathy
DPPP	Dynamic Peak Plantar Pressure	DS	Double Support
ET	Extra Trees	FA	Friedreich's Ataxia
FF	Flat Foot	FI	Freeze Index
FoG	Freezing of Gait	FRQ	Fall Risk Questionnaire
FSM	Finite State Machine	FSR	Force-Sensitive Resistor
Gacc	Gradient Acceleration	GB	Gradient Boosting
Gdece	Gradient Deceleration	GRF	Ground Reaction Forces
GS	Gait Speed	GSTPs	Gait Spatiotemporal Parameters
HC	Healthy Control	HD	Huntington's Disease
HMM	Hidden Markov Model	HO	Heel Off
HR	Heel Rise	HS	Heel Strike
IC	Initial Contact	ICC	Intraclass Correlation Coefficient
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit	IoT	Internet of Things
IS	Initial Swing	ITSV	Inter-limb Time-varying Singular Value
JIA	Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis	KNN	K Nearest Neighbors
LDA	Linear Discriminant Analysis	LLE	Largest Lyapunov Exponent
LR	Loading Response	LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MDS-UPDRS	Movement Disorder Society – Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale	ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron	MoCap	Motion Capture
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging	MS	Multiple Sclerosis
MSE	Multiscale Entropy	MSt	Mid Stance
MSw	Mid Swing	NB	Naive Bayes
NMAE	Normalized Mean Absolute Error	NN	Neural Network
OA	Older Adult	PAD	Peripheral Arterial Disease
PCA	Principal Component Analysis	PD	Parkinson's Disease
PDQ-8	Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire	PER	Piezoelectric Sensor
PLS-DA	Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis	PPP	Peak Plantar Pressure
PPS	Plantar Pressure Sensor	PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PS	Pronation-Supination	PsA	Psoriatic Arthritis
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio	PSw	Pre swing
QDA	Quadratic Discriminant Analysis	RCMSE	Refined Composite Multiscale Entropy
RF	Random Forest	RFE	Recursive Feature Elimination
RMS	Root Mean Square	RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic	ROM	Range of Motion
RQA	Recurrence Quantification Analysis	S	Speed
SampEn	Sample Entropy	SdL	Stride Length
SLT	Synchronization Loss Threshold	SpL	Step Length
SPPP	Segmental Peak Plantar Pressure	SpS	Step Speed
SpT	Step Time	SS	Single Support
StD	Standard Deviation	StP	Stance Phase
SVM	Support Vector Machine	SVM-RBF	Support Vector Machine with RBF Kernel
SwP	Swing Phase	T1DM	Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus
T2DM	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus	TO	Toe Off
TSt	Terminal Stance	TSVD	Time-varying Singular Value Decomposition
TSw	Terminal Swing	TUG	Timed-Up-And-Go Test
Var	Variability	vGRF	Vertical Ground Reaction Forces
Vmax	Maximum Velocity	VPT	Vibration Perception Thresholds
XGB	Extreme Gradient Boosting		

performance. In several subsections of this review, particularly PD diagnosis, severity estimation, FoG detection, gait-phase segmentation, and nonlinear gait-pattern classification, reported accuracies frequently exceed 90%, and in some cases approach 100%. Such results, while encouraging, must be interpreted cautiously. Many were obtained using structured laboratory protocols, speed-matched comparisons,

curated datasets, or within-subject validation, conditions that reduce natural gait variability and can artificially inflate performance. Imbalanced cohorts, where healthy controls often outnumber PD participants or exhibit less variance, further increase the risk of overfitting by simplifying the classification boundary rather than capturing disease-specific gait patterns.

Discrepancies in study design, including sensor placement, number of sensors, and protocol definition also complicate data synthesis and comparability. While lower-back sensors offer a global view of gait, foot-mounted sensors capture step-level events; yet inconsistent application across studies limits the ability to draw unified conclusions. Hardware-related constraints, such as calibration requirements, battery life, and differences in sampling rates across commercial systems, additionally affect reproducibility.

Early detection and continuous monitoring remain core strengths of wearable systems, offering potential for timely interventions that prevent complications and reduce healthcare costs. However, to fully realize this potential, standardized data-collection protocols, harmonized evaluation procedures, and the adoption of publicly available benchmarking datasets are urgently needed. Multi-center external validation is particularly important to assess model performance across diverse settings, sensor platforms, and patient populations. Broader inclusion of heterogeneous participants, across age, disease severity, comorbidities, and daily-life variability, will further improve external validity and support equitable deployment.

Future directions should also explore multimodal data integration, combining gait metrics with physiological indicators like heart rate, glucose variability, or neural biomarkers to develop more holistic and predictive healthcare models. Equally important is the development of unobtrusive, user-friendly wearable systems that balance diagnostic precision with comfort and ease of use. Systems using up to 11 IMUs at different body parts, while data-rich, may reduce user compliance, complicate calibration, and compromise long-term usability. Striking an optimal balance between system complexity, energy efficiency and patient acceptance is essential for long-term adoption in real-world settings, particularly in chronic progressive diseases like PD.

Ultimately, gait analytics is poised to become a core component of precision medicine. Realizing this vision will require continued innovation, interdisciplinary collaboration, methodological refinement and user-centered design to ensure that gait-based technologies are scalable, interpretable, externally validated, reliable, and clinically accessible across the healthcare continuum. With sustained efforts toward methodological rigor and standardization, wearable sensor-based gait analytics can evolve from promising research tools into reliable digital biomarkers for widespread clinical deployment.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, despite challenges related to generalizability across diverse populations, methodological variability, and dependence on rapidly evolving technologies, gait analytics holds meaningful potential for improving the diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment of motor impairments. Variations in sensor design, data-acquisition protocols, and algorithmic strategies pose obstacles to standardization but also foster

opportunities for innovation and tailored solutions. Addressing these challenges requires interdisciplinary collaboration to develop robust, scalable frameworks that enhance reliability and real-world applicability.

The field offers considerable opportunities, particularly in early detection of motor dysfunction and personalized intervention; however, the current body of evidence remains preliminary in several areas. To advance toward clinically reliable and generalizable gait analytics, future work must prioritize: (a) multi-center external validation, (b) standardized benchmarking datasets, (c) harmonized evaluation protocols, and (d) broader inclusion of diverse participant populations, alongside (e) larger and more balanced cohorts, (f) increased use of free-living gait data, (g) standardized sensor configurations, (h) improved model interpretability, and (i) clinically integrated, low-burden wearable systems. With continued advancements in wearable sensors, AI, and data integration, gait analysis may progressively contribute to more individualized and data-informed clinical decision-making. Importantly, the broader impact on patient-centered outcomes, clinical trajectories, and long-term functional improvement has yet to be fully established and requires thorough prospective validation. As such, ongoing research and careful evaluation are essential to confirm the practical benefits and real-world clinical value of gait analytics within modern healthcare and rehabilitation.

APPENDIX LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

This appendix provides a consolidated list of abbreviations used throughout the manuscript.

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